

EDGE EFFECTS IN RESIN MATRIX COMPOSITES WITH CYCLIC ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents and illustrates an approximate solution to determine the edge effects in the skin of resin matrix composite structures exposed to cyclic temperature and moisture conditions during life time. This solution introduces a penetration parameter to characterize the extent of the fluctuating part of the moisture content, and approximate bounds of this fluctuation. These quantities are obtained with very little computing effort. Completing previous results, they constitute a straightforward and precise solution for the long term environmental effects in resin matrix composites. Several examples are presented to assess the validity of the method and to demonstrate its high efficiency compared to the classical step-by-step integration.

Keywords : Cyclic Environmental Conditions, Edge Effects, Long Term Behaviour,
Moisture Content, Penetration Parameter, Resin Matrix Composites

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the most important issues in the use of composite materials is the behaviour of the material due to moisture sorption through long years of service under cyclic environmental conditions. This problem has been extensively investigated, specially for aeronautical structures, to calculate the moisture content in composite materials exposed to air with varying temperature and relative humidity simulating long term service. Classical studies, such as presented by Springer¹⁻³, are based on a numerical step by step computation.

The widespread, simple moisture diffusion model for the computation of the kinetic water sorption is based on Fick's law. The analysis of the moisture content in the composite material can be done with the hypothesis of an instantaneous thermal equilibrium, i.e. the temperature through the thickness of the material is equal to the given external time-dependent temperature. The solution shows the following typical features :

- the fluctuating part decreases very quickly through the thickness of the plate and is actually limited to a very small distance of the surface (edge effects), for any value of time ;
- the transient part decreases with time very quickly in the skin, more and more slowly as the considered position is far away from the surface.

After some time, the solution is consequently composed of a time-periodic part confined within the skin and a limit value of the moisture content in the core. This constant value is of major interest for testing, design or acceptance.

The classical numerical approach reproduces precisely these characteristics of the solution, but involves very long computational times, as with the computer code W8GAIN published by Springer ². Taking benefit of the special features of the solution, we developed and validated in the previous studies (Verchery ⁴, Adda-Bedia et al ⁵) a very fast determination of the moisture content in the core after long term service, i.e. the plateau value or gradient value in the cases of identical or different humidity conditions on both sides of the plate, respectively.

The purpose of this paper is to complete the determination of the moisture concentration parameters through the thickness of the plate. We propose in this paper formulas to determine the penetration parameter, which permits to determine the extent of the edge effects, and approximate bounds for the fluctuating part in the skin of the plate. The form and the period of the cyclic environmental conditions are influent on these parameters which characterize the edge effects.

2. ANALYSIS

2.1 Edge Effects

The diffusivity D is a known cyclic function of the time t , as it is a given function of the temperature T , which itself is a cyclic function of time determined by the cyclic environmental conditions :

$$D = D(t) . \tag{1}$$

Introducing the time integral of the diffusivity over a period τ of this cyclic function :

$$D(\tau) = \int_0^\tau D(t) dt , \tag{2}$$

a penetration parameter (PP in the figures) is defined as :

$$x_0 = \sqrt{\frac{D(\tau)}{\pi}} . \tag{3}$$

As shown by Verchery ⁴, this penetration parameter characterizes the decrement of the fluctuating part from the edge. Table 1 presents the values of the fluctuation along the thickness, compared to the maximum amplitude of variation (obtained at the surface) and to the plateau value. From this table, the edge effect extent (EEE in the figures) is defined as $e_0 = 4 x_0$, for which the fluctuation is less than 2% of the surface and core values.

In the case of same forms of the cyclic conditions with different periods, $\tau^{(1)}$ and $\tau^{(2)}$, the ratios of the penetration parameters and the edge effect extents are found as :

$$\frac{x_0^{(2)}}{x_0^{(1)}} = \frac{e_0^{(2)}}{e_0^{(1)}} = \sqrt{\frac{\tau^{(2)}}{\tau^{(1)}}} , \tag{4}$$

which describes the influence of the cycle duration.

When the thickness is large compared to the penetration parameter, the solution is only dependent on the ratio x/x_0 (reduced position) :

$$c(x,t) = c_r(x/x_0, t) , \tag{5}$$

where c_r is a reduced concentration.

2.2 Bounds for the Fluctuating Part

To bracket the fluctuating part in the boundary layer of the plate, we developed empirical values for the upper and lower bounds of the moisture content $c(x,t)$, based on the following form :

$$A + B \exp(-x/x_0) . \quad (6)$$

The constants A and B are determined by fitting this form with limit values of the moisture contents, i.e. $c(0,t)$ at the surface of the plate and c_0 in the core. It yields to :

$$c_{\text{sup}}(x) = c_0 + [\max c(0,t) - c_0] \exp(-x/x_0) , \quad (7)$$

$$c_{\text{inf}}(x) = c_0 + [\min c(0,t) - c_0] \exp(-x/x_0) , \quad (8)$$

which reduces in the following examples to :

$$c_{\text{inf}}(x) = c_0 [1 - \exp(-x/x_0)] . \quad (9)$$

3. VALIDATION

For the validation of the present method, we have performed numerous numerical studies. We present in this paper three examples with the same form for the variation of the environmental conditions, and different periods : 6 hours, 6 days and 6 weeks.

The variations of temperature and relative humidity retained are shown in Figures 1 and 2, respectively. These environmental conditions are identical to those described by Springer¹ to simulate the 20-year service life of an aircraft. The temperature and humidity were assumed to vary cyclically. For the 6-day period (144 hours), normal atmospheric conditions are active for 123 hours, followed by a flight for 11 hours, and normal atmospheric conditions once more for 10 hours. The relative humidity of the environment was assumed to be constant (82%), except during flight when the relative humidity decreases to zero (Figure 2). The material properties and geometry used in the present studies are summarized in Table 2.

For computation, the present method and the program W8GAIN, programmed in FORTRAN 77, were computed on a workstation (Apollo DN 4500 with a 68030 processor and a floating point accelerator).

3.1. Edge Effects

For validating the present method, we compared our results with those of W8GAIN obtained by the step-by-step integration.

The penetration parameters and the edge effect extents are shown in Figures 3 and 4, for 6-hour cycles and 6-day cycles, respectively. The edge effect extent e_0 , obtained by Equation 3, is in complete agreement with the results of W8GAIN.

The ratios of the edge effect extents e_0 (0.1594 mm for the period of 6 hours, 0.7812 mm for the period of 6 days and 2.067 mm for the period of 6 weeks) are in agreement with Equation 4. Figure 5 compares the edge effects for the various periods.

Table 3 shows a comparison of the CPU computational time of the present method with the W8GAIN program. It gives the times for which a 4-digit precision convergence is reached when computing the limit values of the moisture content in the core of the plate. The results show that, for the present method, the computation time is independent on the period value and up to 20000 times faster than the step-by-step integration.

3.2. Approximate Bounds

Figures 6-8 represent our empirical solutions for the bounds of the fluctuating part obtained by Equations 7-9, compared to the results of W8GAIN for the periods of 6 hours, 6 days and 6 weeks, respectively. They illustrate that the present empirical solutions, which do not involve any computing effort, are acceptable.

4. CONCLUSION

This paper has presented an approximate solution to determine the edge effects in the skin of resin matrix composite structures exposed to cyclic temperature and moisture conditions during life time. This solution introduces the penetration parameter to characterize the extent of the fluctuating part of the moisture content, and approximate bounds of this fluctuation. These quantities are obtained with very little computing effort, out of all comparison with step-by-step integration. Completing previous studies, they constitute a straightforward and precise solution for the long term environmental effects in resin matrix composites. The significant reduction of the computation to obtain the important features of the water sorption can help the life-time studies for polymer matrix composite parts.

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x	0	3 x ₀	4 x ₀	5 x ₀
$(c - c_{\max}) / c_{\max}$	100 %	4.98 %	1.83 %	0.67 %
$(c - c_0) / c_0$	72 %	3.61 %	1.33 %	0.49 %

Table 1 - Moisture concentration c along the thickness compared to the maximum amplitude of the variation c_{\max} and to the plateau value c_0 .

Thickness, mm	h = 12.7
Diffusivity, mm ² /sec	D = 252 exp(-6794 / T), T : temperature (°K)
Maximum moisture as a function of relative humidity, %	M = 0.0205 H, H : relative humidity (%)

Table 2 - Geometry and material properties, from Springer 1.

Period	Present method	W8GAIN	Ratio
6 hours	1.474 sec	8 h 38 min 41 sec	21113
6 days	1.463 sec	33 min 59 sec	1394
6 weeks	1.466 sec	24 min 23 sec	998

Table 3 - Computation times to obtain the limit values with a 4-digit precision.

Figure 1. Ambient temperature versus reduced time : $t_r = t/(6 \text{ hours})$, $t/(6 \text{ days})$, $t/(6 \text{ weeks})$.

Figure 2. Ambient relative humidity versus reduced time : $t_r = t/(6 \text{ hours})$, $t/(6 \text{ days})$, $t/(6 \text{ weeks})$.

Figure 3. Moisture content at the left side of the plate for 6 hours at the different points (A-H) presented in Figures 1 and 2. PP and EEE are respectively Parameter Penetration and Edge Effect Extent. $x_0 = 0.03986$.

Figure 4. Moisture content at the left side of the plate for 6 days at the different points (A-H) presented in Figures 1 and 2. PP and EEE are respectively Parameter Penetration and Edge Effect Extent. $x_0 = 0.1953$.

Figure 5. Moisture content at the left side of the plate for 6-hour, 6-day and 6-week cycles. EEE is for the Edge Effect Extent. The curves were obtained from W8GAIN at the end of the cycles (point H shown in Figures 1 and 2).

6-hour cycles

Figure 6. Approximate bounds for the fluctuating part of the moisture content in the skin of the plate (6-hour cycles).

Figure 7. Approximate bounds for the fluctuating part of the moisture content in the skin of the plate (6-day cycles).

Figure 8. Approximate bounds for the fluctuating part of the moisture content in the skin of the plate (6-week cycles).